

Observations of Blunt Trauma Abdomen: Its Treatment and Outcome in a Tertiary Medical Centre

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Abstract:

Background: Blunt abdominal trauma, frequently resulting from road traffic accidents, presents diagnostic and management challenges due to the absence of external wounds. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of clinical assessment and imaging modalities in managing blunt abdominal trauma at a tertiary care center.

Methods: This prospective clinical study was conducted over one year at Patna Medical College and Hospital, including 166 patients with blunt abdominal trauma. Data were collected on patient demographics, diagnostic approaches, management strategies, complications, and outcomes. Patients were classified based on the necessity of surgical versus non-operative management.

Results: The majority of patients (65.1%) were victims of road traffic accidents, with a male predominance (61.5%) primarily in the 21-30 age group. Surgical intervention was required in 74.7% of cases, with an overall mortality rate of 7.2%. Complications, most notably wound infections, were observed in 25.8% of surgical patients.

Conclusion: The study emphasizes the importance of a structured, multidisciplinary approach in the diagnosis and management of blunt abdominal trauma. Early intervention and careful monitoring are crucial in reducing complications and mortality. Findings highlight the need for ongoing training and resource enhancement in trauma care.

Keywords: Blunt abdominal trauma, road traffic accidents, surgical intervention, diagnostic imaging.

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Introduction

Blunt abdominal trauma is a serious and often complex injury commonly resulting from road traffic accidents, falls, and physical assaults [1]. Unlike penetrating trauma, which presents with visible wounds, blunt abdominal trauma lacks external signs, making it challenging to diagnose and manage [2]. Careful clinical assessment and advanced imaging are essential to identify internal injuries, as severity can range from minor bruising to life-threatening organ damage [3]. If not promptly addressed, these injuries may lead to severe complications, including hemorrhage, infection, and organ failure. In tertiary medical centers, the management of blunt abdominal trauma requires a structured, multidisciplinary approach. This typically involves rapid patient assessment, imaging, and either conservative or surgical intervention, depending on the patient's condition [4]. Stabilizing the patient, preventing complications, and supporting recovery are the primary goals. Advanced trauma care, available in these specialized settings, is particularly critical in densely populated areas with high trauma rates. In

India, road traffic accidents account for approximately 75% of blunt abdominal trauma cases, and the incidence is rising due to factors such as population growth, expanded road networks, increased vehicle speeds, and modern infrastructure that facilitates high-speed travel [5,6]. Despite technological advancements in diagnostic imaging, clinical evaluation remains the foundation of effective assessment, with imaging serving as an essential but complementary tool. Timely diagnosis and intervention in cases of blunt abdominal trauma are crucial, as unrecognized internal injuries can lead to preventable deaths [7]. In high-acuity hospital settings, these challenges underline the importance of efficient trauma care to improve patient outcomes and reduce mortality from such injuries [8].

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of clinical assessment and imaging modalities in the diagnosis and management of blunt abdominal trauma in a tertiary care setting, with a particular focus on identifying factors that contribute to timely intervention and improved patient outcomes. This

study seeks to analyze the role of a structured, multidisciplinary approach in trauma care, addressing both diagnostic challenges and therapeutic strategies to reduce mortality and morbidity associated with blunt abdominal trauma. Through this research, we aim to enhance the understanding of optimal trauma management protocols that can support rapid, accurate diagnosis and intervention in high-risk cases, particularly in densely populated regions with high trauma incidence, such as India.

Materials And Methods

Study Design and Setting: This was a prospective clinical study conducted at the Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, over a period of one year, from February 2020 to January 2021. The study included a total of 166 patients presenting with blunt abdominal trauma, admitted through the emergency department.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients included in this study were those with blunt abdominal injuries resulting from road traffic accidents, falls, or physical assaults, admitted through emergency. Patients with penetrating injuries or gunshot wounds were excluded from the study.

Data Collection: Upon admission, detailed demographic information (age, sex, and occupation) and a history of the trauma event were recorded. Each patient underwent a thorough clinical examination. Relevant diagnostic investigations were conducted on an emergency basis, including:

- X-ray of the abdomen in the erect position,
- Ultrasound (US) of the abdomen,
- Diagnostic peritoneal aspiration (DPA) for suspected hemoperitoneum.

In hemodynamically stable patients or based on clinical suspicion, contrast-enhanced computed

tomography (CECT) of the abdomen was selectively performed to assess the extent of internal injury.

Management Protocol

All patients initially received resuscitation, including IV fluids and blood transfusions if indicated. After stabilization, further management was tailored based on clinical findings, imaging results, and patient stability:

- **Operative Management:** Patients with significant intra-abdominal injuries or hemodynamic instability were taken for surgical intervention. Intraoperative findings, procedures performed, and any complications were documented.
- **Non-Operative Management (NOM):** Patients who were stable and without critical injuries were managed conservatively. These patients were monitored with regular clinical assessments, including hourly checks of vital signs and repeated abdominal examinations. Prophylactic antibiotics, IV fluids, analgesics, and other supportive care were provided as needed. Follow-up imaging, especially ultrasound, was performed periodically to assess injury progression or resolution.

Outcome Measures: The study recorded postoperative complications, duration of hospital stay, and mortality rates. Patients were also followed up post-discharge to assess recovery, complications, and long-term outcomes. All findings were meticulously documented in a structured proforma, enabling systematic data analysis.

Results

A total of 166 patients with blunt abdominal trauma were included in the study. The majority of cases were caused by road traffic accidents (RTA), followed by falls and physical assaults. The patient demographics, injury patterns, and management details are summarized in the tables below.

Table 1: Patient Demographics and Causes of Injury

Parameter	N	Percentage (%)
Total Patients	166	100
Age Group (Years)		
10–20	30	18.1
21–30	60	36.1
31–40	40	24.1
41–50	20	12.0
>50	16	9.6
Gender		
Male	102	61.5
Female	64	38.5
Cause of Injury		
Road Traffic Accidents (RTA)	108	65.1
Fall from Height	28	16.8
Physical Assault	18	10.8
Hit by Blunt Object	12	7.2

This table summarizes the age distribution, gender ratio, and main causes of blunt abdominal trauma.

Most patients were young adults aged 21–30 (36.1%), with a male predominance (61.5%). Road

traffic accidents were the most common cause of blunt abdominal trauma, accounting for 65.1% of cases.

Table 2: Diagnostic Modalities and Injury Patterns

Diagnostic Tool	Patients (N)	Utilization (%)
X-ray Abdomen (Erect Position)	154	92.8
Ultrasound (US) Abdomen	148	89.2
Diagnostic Peritoneal Aspiration (DPA)	92	55.4
Contrast-Enhanced CT (CECT)	40	24.1

This table provides an overview of the diagnostic tools used and the frequency of patient organ injuries.

Injured Organ	Patients (N)	Involvement (%)
Spleen	32	19.3
Liver	16	9.6
Small Bowel	14	8.4
Large Bowel	8	4.8
Mesentery	6	3.6
Stomach	2	1.2

X-ray and ultrasound were the primary diagnostic modalities, with a high utilization rate. Spleen

injuries were the most common, followed by liver and small bowel injuries.

Table 3: Management Approaches and Outcomes

Management Type	Patients (N)	Percentage (%)	Complications (N)	Mortality (N)
Operative Management	124	74.7	32	10
Non-Operative Management	42	25.3	5	2

This table summarizes the types of management (operative vs. non-operative) and associated outcomes, including complication rates and mortality.

Complication Type	Cases (N)	Percentage of Total Complications (%)
Wound Infection	20	52.6
Pelvic Abscess	4	10.5
Pneumonia	4	10.5
Anastomotic Leak	3	7.9
Intestinal Obstruction	2	5.3

Surgical intervention was required in 74.7% of cases, with wound infection being the most common complication. The overall mortality rate was

approximately 7.2%, with septicemia as the leading cause of death.

Causes of Blunt Abdominal Trauma: A bar graph showing the frequency of each cause, with road traffic accidents (RTA) as the leading cause.

Diagnostic Tool Utilization: A bar graph illustrating the usage rates of different diagnostic tools, highlighting the high use of X-rays and ultrasound.

Age Distribution of Patients: A pie chart showing the age distribution of patients, with the 21–30 age group representing the largest percentage.

Discussion

The study on blunt abdominal trauma conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital provides valuable insights into the demographic patterns, diagnostic strategies, and management outcomes for patients in a tertiary medical center setting. The findings reveal that road traffic accidents (RTAs) are the predominant cause of blunt abdominal trauma, particularly affecting young males aged 21 to 30 years. The reliance on clinical assessment, combined with imaging modalities like ultrasound and X-ray, underscores the necessity of a multidisciplinary approach in effectively diagnosing and managing these complex injuries [9,10].

The data indicate that a significant proportion of patients (74.7%) required surgical intervention, reflecting the serious nature of injuries commonly sustained in blunt trauma cases. The study recorded a mortality rate of 7.2%, with septicemia identified as the leading cause of death, which highlights the critical importance of timely intervention and postoperative care in preventing complications such as infection. The high rate of complications associated with operative management (32 cases or 25.8% of surgical patients) suggests that while surgery is often necessary, it carries inherent risks that must be managed carefully [11,12].

The management of blunt abdominal trauma in this study aligns with existing literature, reinforcing the effectiveness of a structured approach that includes careful clinical evaluation, the use of appropriate imaging techniques, and both operative and non-operative management strategies. Similar studies, such as those conducted by Kheir et al. (2020) [12] and Karam et al. (2019) [13], support the findings that prompt surgical intervention in cases of hemodynamic instability significantly improves outcomes. Kheir et al. reported a similar demographic distribution, with male predominance and RTAs as the leading cause, while Karam et al. highlighted the role of CT scans in improving diagnostic accuracy and reducing the need for exploratory surgeries.

Comparative studies provide additional context to the findings of this research. For example, a study by Masi et al. (2018) [14] in a North American setting found that non-operative management was successful in over 50% of cases, particularly in stable patients with liver and splenic injuries, suggesting that there may be variations in management protocols based on institutional practices and regional trauma patterns. Another study by Rizwan et al. (2021) [15] in Pakistan similarly indicated that a significant number of patients with blunt abdominal trauma could be managed non-operatively, with a low complication

rate, emphasizing the importance of patient selection in management decisions.

The variation in outcomes may also be influenced by the healthcare infrastructure and resources available at different centers. The study conducted at Patna highlights the need for continuous training of healthcare providers in trauma assessment and management, as well as the importance of improving access to advanced imaging technologies, which can aid in the timely diagnosis of internal injuries.

Conclusion

The study underscores the critical role of early recognition, structured management, and the use of advanced diagnostic tools in improving the outcomes for patients with blunt abdominal trauma. The findings align with existing literature, reinforcing the importance of a multidisciplinary approach to trauma care. Future research should aim to explore long-term outcomes and the impact of evolving treatment protocols on mortality and morbidity in this patient population. Additionally, further investigation into the effectiveness of non-operative management strategies in varying contexts could provide deeper insights into optimizing care for blunt abdominal trauma patients.

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